

Culture and Identity in Jhumpa Lahiri's 'Unaccustomed Earth'

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Abstract

*Jhumpa Lahiri (1967-), born in England to Bengali parents and raised in America, has been categorised as an Indian-American, post-modern, post-colonial, and Indian writer. The process of naming Lahiri has been protracted and complex. Nevertheless, the identity she selects for herself is distinct. She desires to be acknowledged solely as an American writer. Lahiri employs Russian literature as a means to build an identity for her main character. In her second collection of short stories, titled *Unaccustomed Earth* (2008), Lahiri utilises the American writer Nathaniel Hawthorne not only to propose the title and epigraph for the collection but also to assert her inclusion in the American literary canon, as proposed by Ambreen Hai in "Re-Rooting Families: The Alter/Natal as the Central Dynamic of Jhumpa Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth*."*

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Introduction

In Jhumpa Lahiri's debut novel, *The Namesake*, the protagonist is named after the renowned Russian writer Nikolai Gogol (1809-1852). Throughout his life, the protagonist's father often mentions Gogol's short story, *The Overcoat*, until his death. In his article titled "Names Can Wait: The Misnaming of the South Asian Diaspora in Theory and Practice," Amardeep Singh suggests that the peculiar name "Gogol" in *The Overcoat* symbolizes the unfamiliarity and strangeness of the Indian immigrant experience in the United States. Lahiri's own life reflects the reality that the children of immigrants often find themselves in a state of geographical and cultural uncertainty. Although she resides in the United States, she does not fully experience American citizenship, partly due to the lack of recognition by others. During her childhood, she enjoyed certain privileges, but she also had to navigate the process of

familiarizing herself with and adjusting to American values and beliefs, which were often at odds with those upheld in her household.

From the beginning of her writing career, Lahiri concentrated on the experiences of first and second-generation Bengali immigrants in the United States, a subject that was relatively new to American readers at the time. Reflecting on her time in the United States, she observed that during her upbringing in the 1970s, India was largely unknown to most Americans, who perceived it as distant and unfamiliar. When she accompanied her parents to Calcutta, acquaintances and educators would often comment on how daunting it must have been for her to be forced to travel to India. As a young child, she also traveled to her birthplace, London, where India was not seen as an exotic location due to its colonial history. In contrast, in the United States, England was viewed differently—still perceived as a distant place, but one that held some presence in the collective awareness. England was a familiar concept, akin to something one might encounter in a Jane Austen novel, but not in the works of American authors like Hawthorne or Melville.

Lahiri desires an American identity that resembles Hawthorne's concept of the cloak. In numerous interviews, she stressed that individuals would persist in labelling her as Indian and interpreting her novels solely about the distinctive experiences of Indian-Americans in America. During an interview in August 2009 in New York, she was queried about the current state of her initial compilation of short stories. About *Interpreter of Maladies* (1999) and other Asian-American writers who emerged following the immigrant influx after 1965, she stated:

I believe that my writing will inevitably be considered in the same category as other writers of Indian origin and Indian writers...During interviews, a significant portion of my time is dedicated to clarifying that I am not of Indian origin. There is a significant readership that, upon seeing my book, its cover, design, motifs, and my name, automatically assumes that I am Indian or conforms to their preconceived notion of what it means to be Indian, assuming that I was born and raised there and that I am an outsider in this country (Leyda 71).

Lahiri's writings are effective because she avoids using exoticism or a polished style to captivate her readers. Instead, her works can be seen through the lenses of orientalism, post-

colonialism, and diaspora. Lahiri, a second-generation diasporic writer, embodies in the cultural discourse the issues of alienation, displacement, rootlessness, frustration, fragmentation, and marginalisation. The excessive focus on the diasporic experience has caused readers to disregard the artistic merit of her work. Lahiri explicitly refutes the notion of being confined to a narrow classification and underscores her focus on crafting characters that are uniquely individual rather than solely representing the diaspora. Furthermore, she emphasises that her writing delves into the universal struggles of human existence rather than being limited to a particular cultural experience. She is primarily interested in exploring the psychological depths of characters and the complex challenges of the human condition (Hemlata 215). This treatment and subject matter are characteristic of Hawthorne's style, focusing on human nature and the human heart.

Similar to Lahiri, Hawthorne, a New Englander, was renowned for expressing that "New England was a landmass that his heart could fully encompass" (Taylor 153). Despite his close relationship with the Pilgrim fathers, he maintained a distance from them. He appended the letter "w" to his surname to disassociate himself from his forebears. He would refer to them as "very unhappy individuals". He expressed gratitude to God for them and thereafter expressed gratitude to God for the significant temporal distance between each generation and them. Advocating the practice of transplantation, Lahiri believed that deeply rooted problems could only be resolved by gradual transformation inside the core of human nature. Lahiri harboured a similar ambivalence towards her Indian roots. Similar to Hawthorne, she also altered her name. Jhumpa was her family's affectionate nickname for her, but she decided to adopt it as her official name based on her American school teacher's advice. This decision was influenced by the fact that Jhumpa was easier to say compared to her formal name, Nilanjana Sudeshna. Nevertheless, she was aware of the disparity between her family's lifestyle and the American way of life that she admired. In 2006, she expressed, "I had immense pressure to embody both loyalty to my cultural heritage and proficiency in the modern American society." (Online Interview) Speaking Bengali and eating rice with her two fingers appeared completely unfamiliar to her, and she made an effort to conceal these practices from her American pals. By portraying the experiences of American-born children of Indian immigrants from the middle class, sometimes referred to as ABCD (American-Born Confused Desi), Lahiri also embodies

the cultural norms and values of well-educated individuals in America, regardless of their Indian or non-Indian background. Her stories about marriage, divorce, parenthood, and coping with the loss of her ageing parents are far from being exotic. Her writing ultimately portrays an astute depiction of the lifestyle of the upper-middle class

Jhumpa Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth* has been influenced by nineteenth-century American writers, such as Nathaniel Hawthorne. In her collection "Unaccustomed Earth," Lahiri incorporates the American writer Nathaniel Hawthorne to imply the title, primary topic, and epigraph. The novel *Unaccustomed Earth* commences with an epigraph extracted from the *Custom House* segment of *The Scarlet Letter*, which asserts that human nature, akin to a potato, can not thrive if it is continuously cultivated in the same exhausted soil over numerous generations. My children have been born in different areas, and as far as I can influence their future, they will establish themselves in unfamiliar territories. Lahiri's declaration signifies her affiliation with the American literary canon rather than aligning herself with postcolonial or ethnic writers (Arjopalo 12). In her article "Ethnicity and Intertextuality in Jhumpa Lahiri's Oeuvre" published in the book *Naming Jhumpa Lahiri: Canons and Controversies*, Karen M. Cardozo proposes that Lahiri used intertextuality, specifically referencing Hawthorne's work, to connect the general and the particular aspects of her writing (3). The author claims that Lahiri, by paraphrasing Hawthorne, surpasses her ethnic identity and instead presents a bold attempt to assert her belonging to America. In addition, to solidify her American identity, the author develops the three interconnected stories in the second part of the collection titled "Hema and Kaushik" following the pattern of Hester and Dimmesdale.

Lahiri reversed the chronological order of events in *The Scarlet Letter*. Instead of commencing with the current "Custom House" section, which is situated in nineteenth-century Massachusetts, and subsequently delving into the past to recount the tale of the scarlet letter, which unfolds in the seventeenth century, Lahiri opts to place the events of her initial two stories in the past and the final one in the present. The trilogy recounts the initial encounter of the major characters in the past, followed by their subsequent individual paths until they reunite and cultivate their romantic relationship, which reaches its culmination in the present. Lahiri organises her short stories in the sequence of *Once in a Lifetime*, *Year's End*, and *Going Ashore*. When reading in this sequence, we might see the first two pieces as merely establishing the

essential context for the main piece, namely, *Going Ashore*. *Once in a Lifetime* and *Year's End*" are synonymous with the *Custom House* segment in Hawthorne's work. If we read *Going Ashore*, *Once in a Lifetime*, and *Year's End* in reverse sequence, we will obtain a reimagining of *The Scarlet Letter*. Both *Once in a Lifetime* and *Year's End* are situated in the historical period.

The book chronicles the historical account of the friendship between Hema and Kaushik's family, Hema's infatuation with Kaushik, the illness of Kaushik's mother, and his subsequent life following her demise. The initial occurrence of *Once in a Lifetime* is narrated by Hema, a thirteen-year-old, to Kaushik during the period when his family was residing with hers, contemplating a move to the United States. Alternatively, it may be titled "Once Upon a Time" due to its focus on the origins and the narrative of Hema and Kaushik's relationship. The second story, titled *Year's End*, is narrated by the adult Kaushik to Hema. He recounts his experiences at college, his inability to overcome his mother's death, and his father's subsequent marriage. The final story, "Going Ashore," takes place in the present. The all-knowing narrator informs us about the revival of Hema and Kaushik's love affair in Rome. Hema provides further lines detailing her marriage to another guy and her profound astonishment at learning of Kaushik's sudden demise. *The Scarlet Letter* begins in nineteenth-century Massachusetts, where the narrator discovers a scarlet letter, along with some old documents while working in the *Customs House*. Following extensive inquiry, he proceeds to recount the narrative of the letter, which transpired two centuries ago in New England.

The narrative explores the repercussions of their reconciliation and their eventual parting. Hema remains steadfast in her decision to proceed with her traditional marriage to Navin, an Indian-American guy whom she is not well acquainted with, despite Kaushik's rejection of her proposal. Meanwhile, Kaushik, who remains desperate and disoriented, tragically perishes in a tsunami while on vacation in Thailand.

The conclusion of *The Scarlet Letter* is comparable. Dimmesdale succumbs to defeat and perishes due to a broken spirit and strong emotions resulting from the overwhelming remorse and helplessness he experiences for not confessing his sin and accepting his moral obligation towards Hester and his daughter Pearl. In contrast, Hester, who is defiant and resistant to authority, manages to endure despite the unfavourable circumstances due to her

ability to deal with the repercussions of her actions and progress in her life, albeit with some sacrifices. Hawthorne depicts the initial introduction of the character in the novella, as well as her subsequent humiliation in the marketplace, which is witnessed by the public.

She exhibited a refined and elegant demeanour, in line with the traditional standards of feminine grace and sophistication in that era. This was marked by a particular level of poise and gravitas. As she emerged from the prison, Hester Prynne had never looked more elegant and refined, according to the traditional understanding of the term "lady-like."

The individuals who were previously acquainted with her and had anticipated seeing her appearance diminished and concealed by a calamitous situation were amazed, and even alarmed, to observe how her physical attractiveness radiated and created an aura around the tragedy and disgrace that surrounded her (53).

Lahiri challenges the stereotype of Asian-American men by portraying them as constantly battling feelings of guilt and failure. On the other hand, her female characters find freedom and independence, while still adhering to traditional values by relying on their parents for support (Hemlata 35). In her essay "Feminising Men? Moving Beyond Asian American Literary Gender Wars in Jhumpa Lahiri's Fiction" in the book *Naming Jhumpa Lahiri: Canons and Controversies*, Lavina Dhingra argues that Jhumpa Lahiri's writings go beyond and question the conventional portrayal of Bengali American men found in the works of Asian American authors from the 1980s and 1990s (136).

Lahiri's depiction of male characters includes an added layer of emotional sensitivity and self-expression, presenting a new paradigm of a sensitive, emotionally fragile, and feminised guy for the twenty-first century (152). Unlike other Asian American women writers such as Maxine Hong Kingston, who is of Chinese-American descent and was born in 1940, and Bharati Mukherjee, who is of Indian-American descent and was also born in 1940, Lahiri diverges from the focus on "the woman warrior syndrome" by exploring themes beyond gender discrimination and arranged marriages. Instead, Lahiri portrays a diverse array of male protagonists...Therefore, she successfully elicits empathy from even female readers for [them]. (139)

Kaushik is emotionally vulnerable following the demise of his mother. His entire existence crumbles in the aftermath of her demise. He continuously recalls her and meticulously recollects every aspect of their shared existence. During the "Year's End," every aspect of his surroundings takes on a sentimental significance for him as it evokes memories of her: the swimming pool, the kitchen, the cuisine, and so on. On Christmas Eve, he engages in arguments with his step sisters due to his strong aversion towards the replacement of his mother by another lady who is unlike his mother in terms of beauty and sophistication. During a moment of emotional outburst, he expresses his intense dislike for his stepsisters Rupa and Piu, as they innocently go through his mother's photo album.

"You lack the authority to observe those," I informed them.

"They are not your possessions, do you comprehend?"

Rupa nodded, visibly shivering as if affected by the cold, while Piu's lips were firmly pushed together. Tears streamed down their faces while I continued to speak, uttering words that should not have been spoken, should not have been heard. "You have witnessed firsthand the exquisite beauty of my mother." How much more aesthetically pleasing and refined than yours? Your mother is nothing in comparison. I simply require a servant to launder my father's garments and prepare him meals. "That is the whole purpose for her presence, the sole purpose for the presence of both of you." (287)

At Kauskik's graduation ceremony, his father offered him guidance, saying, "Kaushik, we are both progressing and it is time for you to do the same...Uncharted pathways to discover. (293) His father progressed by starting a new life with a young lady from India who had two young girls. He relocated to a new residence just outside of New England. Kaushik departed hastily while fleeing. He deliberately refrained from visiting the United States of America, however, he deeply cherished and preserved every memory of his homeland and his mother. He frequently changed jobs and relocated frequently. He was unable to maintain a long-term relationship with any woman until he coincidentally saw Hema in Rome. She was the sole individual he had encountered in his adult life who comprehended his history, and she was the only woman he desired to maintain a connection with. Kaushik expressed his envy in response to Hema's remarks about a couple they observed in Rome who would reside together in one

location indefinitely. He remarked, "I have never experienced such a strong sense of belonging to any particular place" (p320). Previously, the writer portrayed him as a nomad traversing over North and South America, Africa, the Middle East, Europe, and ultimately Asia. His career as a photojournalist commenced almost two decades ago, following the passing of his mother. During this time, he travelled through Latin America, sustaining himself with the inheritance his father bestowed upon him upon the completion of his studies. This evokes memories of Dimmesdale's late-night vigils and covert errands, during which he carried the weight of concealing his involvement in Hester's adultery and his moral weakness in failing to reveal his role. The vigils symbolise his profound sense of powerlessness in the face of the absence of self-esteem, affection, and belief. Years after their previous romantic encounter, Dimmedale and Hester meet in private as lovers in the forest. Dimmedale expresses his intense emotional pain to Hester during their conversation.

"I feel an increased amount of misery, Hester!-only an increased amount of misery!" responded the clergyman, with a cruel smile. "Regarding any perceived good that I may accomplish, I have no confidence in its validity." It is undoubtedly a hallucination. What impact can a very troubled individual, such as me, have on the salvation of other individuals? The user's text is rewritten in a manner that is direct and concise. If only the people's respect could be transformed into contempt and animosity! Do you consider it a source of comfort, Hester, that I have to stand in my pulpit and face the gaze of so many people looking up at me as if my face were radiating the brightness of heaven!-...and then look within myself and see the dark truth of what they admire? (191)

His emotional, bodily, and psychological anguish came to an end with his premature and abrupt demise on the scaffold, following his confession of sin and the disruption of his plan to elope with Hester and Pearl to begin a new life in Europe.

Hema, the prototype of Hester, attains both financial and intellectual autonomy through the acquisition of her Ph.D. and the acquisition of a house in her name. It is worth noting that Hema and Hester share the same initials. She has terminated a decade-long extramarital relationship with a married American guy named Julian after she came to the realisation that they do not have a prospective future together. She must consent to a conventional marriage

that has been organised by her parents. She is currently betrothed to Navin and they plan to marry in India in a few months. She has become dissatisfied with her existence. She desires to establish a stable life and longs to start a family, which neither Julian nor Kauskik can provide. Hema, a lady in her mid-thirties, no longer relies on luck when it comes to finding love. Instead, she takes pleasure in the feeling of "assurance" that accompanies her arranged marriage (Bollinger 494). When questioned by Kaushik about her decision to marry a man she did not love, she responded, "I believed it may resolve the issues" (313).

Hema exemplifies the archetype of the traditional and loyal Indian daughter, who, despite her scholastic achievements, nonetheless aspires to establish a marital union. She desires to attain an equilibrium between her requirements for stability and autonomy. She journeys to Italy to be solitary, but during her time in Rome, she adheres to a consistent daily schedule and even dines at the same restaurant every day (Arjopalo 42). Hema resides in a state of nostalgia. She specialises in the study of the Etruscans, an ancient civilisation in Rome, and has a strong affinity towards Kaushik due to their common history. However, her recent relationship with Kaushik in Rome has made her come to the realisation that she can never regain or recover the past. According to Yun (142), the bangle she got from her grandmother, which she lost at Customs in Rome, symbolises her complete detachment from her unhappy past and her anticipation of a fresh start in life. Through her marriage in the concluding pages of the book, she has the sensation of disembarking and physically reconnecting with the solid ground. She finally arrives at the desired shoreline, however not accompanied by the ideal partner, somebody one might encounter only once in a lifetime. However, towards the end of the year, Kaushik found himself engulfed by the waves of the Indian Ocean, which were as pleasant and inviting as a bath. He released his grip when his feet made contact with the ground. (133).

Hema's occupation and marriage serve as manifestations of her efforts to reconcile with her past, seeking resolution and comprehension of the present. She can sustain herself independently, but she no longer desires to do so. She turns to traditional marriage as a means of improving her self-esteem and honour (Arjopalo 43). While Hema is characterised by her individuality and passion, Hester Prynne, on the other hand, is portrayed as defiant and rebellious. Like Hema, she too sought to regain her dignity, but with a distinct approach. In a

thought-provoking analysis of the impact of Hawthorne on Lahiri, Rehnuma Sazzad proposes that Hawthorne's novel, *The Scarlet Letter*, takes place in seventeenth-century Massachusetts, amidst the rigid Puritanical regulations. The protagonist, Hester, faces the challenge of reclaiming her dignity, which has been taken away due to the scarlet letter (A) she is compelled to wear around her neck as a symbol of her transgression. While Lahiri's characters may not be as defiant as Hawthorne's protagonist, Hester, they nonetheless face numerous challenges in Massachusetts in the twenty-first century. Despite their diligent efforts to achieve success in their careers, they are unable to resist the temptation represented by Hester's emblem of infidelity. Although they lead a seemingly respectable existence, they experience the torment of dissatisfaction. Lahiri's utilisation of Hawthorne's work highlights the fact that the unexpressed symbol 'A' on her characters' hearts symbolises the enduring human desire for love and the chaos it causes in a hostile setting (54).

Hema's scarlet letter represents her enduring extramarital relationship with Julian in the United States, as well as her profound and ingrained affection for Kaushik, which reached its peak during their brief but intense romance in Rome. There is speculation that she is carrying Kaushik's child, rather than her husband Navin's. "Although Hema acknowledged that Kaushik was your child, she clarified in the last lines of the novella that this was not the actual situation," "We had exercised caution, and you had not left any trace" (333). Kaushik's undisclosed crimson symbol is his intense longing for his adored mother and his affection for Hema.

Jhumpa Lahiri provides a concise overview of the impact that Nathaniel Hawthorne had on her book *Unaccustomed Earth*:

While composing these pieces, I immersed myself in a substantial amount of Hawthorne's literature. The choice to situate the last narrative in Rome was influenced by my reading of *The Marble Faun*, which sparked the concept of placing American characters in the Roman environment. Personally, due to my upbringing in New England, I had a deep understanding of Nathaniel Hawthorne's identity and his significance in the local culture. During my upbringing, I consistently perceived a distinct separation between my world, my family, and the world symbolised by Hawthorne. He embodied the legacy of exceptional American literature. As an adult and a writer, it was a highly intense experience for me to re-read his work. I came across

a paragraph, known as an epigraph, and I immediately recognised how those words resonated with my own life, upbringing, and now my work as a writer (Leyd 79)

Hawthorne's influence on Lahiri and Lahiri's interpretation of Hawthorne cannot be adequately expressed by any other terms. In the section titled "Hema and Kaushik" in Lahiri's book, Lahiri vividly portrays the impact of influence. As one reads more, they discover more similarities between the two books. While Hawthorne's work explores the influence of a letter, Lahiri's book delves into the significance of reading and reinterpreting that letter. This has allowed her name to be associated with esteemed writers such as Hawthorne, and potentially be recognised as one of the greats, akin to him.

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